

SMARTNESS strengthens its position as an innovation hub and inaugurates 5G Studio at Unicamp

Center supported by FAPESP and Ericsson expands experimentation infrastructure and reinforces Brazil's leadership in 5G and 6G technologies

Approaching its third year of operation, the SMARTNESS 2030 Engineering Research Center (CPE), supported by FAPESP and Ericsson, has consolidated itself as one of Brazil's leading research and innovation hubs in 5G and 6G networks. To celebrate this trajectory and mark the beginning of a new phase of technological experimentation, the Center will inaugurate the **SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G)** on **December 3, 2025, at 4:00 p.m.**, in the **Congregation Hall of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (FEEC) at Unicamp**, in Campinas, São Paulo.

During the ceremony, attendees will be able to explore the new SS5G laboratory facilities and experience interactive and immersive demonstrations of research conducted at the Center. The program will feature experiments showcasing how advances in **5G technologies and Edge Computing** can transform the way people, devices, and systems connect.

A new space for experimentation and collaboration

The **SMARTNESS Studio 5G** was conceived as an environment dedicated to the demonstration, training, and prototyping of applications based on 5G, edge computing, artificial intelligence, and programmable networks, fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and society.

Located within the **LEMAC laboratory** at FEEC/Unicamp, the space aims to accelerate the development of practical use cases and pilot experiments—key elements for advancing next-generation mobile networks and for training highly qualified professionals in emerging technologies.

"The reach of SMARTNESS extends from research institutions to industry, which gives my research greater robustness through the different perspectives of the professionals involved," says **Arthur Simas**, a PhD candidate conducting research in neuromorphic computing and next-generation networks.

To enable research of this scope, the SS5G is equipped with a **dedicated Ericsson Private 5G (EP5G) network**, designed to boost the Center's academic research and partnerships.

"The 5G Studio marks the beginning of a new phase for SMARTNESS. With a private 5G network, we now have a secure and fully controllable environment to experimentally

validate new technologies, concepts, and advanced applications for future communication networks,” highlights **Dr. Maria Valéria Marquezini**, Vice-Director of SMARTNESS.

The SS5G initiative is the result of a partnership between **Unicamp, Ericsson, and NEC** in the implementation of network solutions. **NEC** acts as the system integrator, bringing its extensive experience in complex network projects of various scales.

The **Ericsson EP5G private network** represents a significant advancement for Unicamp’s innovation ecosystem, offering ultra-high-performance connectivity, security, and reliability for critical applications. With **low latency, high data throughput, and full control over network resources**, the infrastructure enables advanced experiments in areas such as the **Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, autonomous networks, and industrial applications**.

With this infrastructure, the **SMARTNESS Studio 5G** is established as a living space for learning, experimentation, and co-creation—serving as a bridge between the present of 5G and the future of 6G.

Research shaping the future of connectivity

SMARTNESS is dedicated to research and development of intelligent networks and services that will shape the future of telecommunications through 2030. Its activities focus on 5G technologies and their evolution toward 6G, covering areas such as the **Internet of Senses** and **intelligent networks for industrial and urban applications**.

With a **total investment of BRL 56 million**, the Center aims to position Brazil at the forefront of global technological innovation, strengthening the interaction between science, industry, and society.

“In addition to consolidating itself as a key milestone for research and development, the laboratory will serve as an important link between academia and the telecommunications technology sector, opening opportunities for diverse university–industry partnership models,” says **Dr. Eduardo Sartori**, Technology Transfer and Innovation Manager at SMARTNESS.

Headquartered at **FEEC/Unicamp**, SMARTNESS promotes collaboration among researchers, engineers, and companies, driving studies that range from advanced network infrastructure to new digital applications with the potential to transform society.

The Center is the result of a partnership between **FAPESP** and **Ericsson** and brings together researchers from **Unicamp, USP, UFSCar**, and more than **15 partner institutions** in Brazil, as well as international collaborations.

Brazil at the forefront of 6G

The development of **6G** represents a strategic opportunity for Brazil to move beyond being a technology consumer and become a producer of cutting-edge knowledge and innovation. Achieving this goal requires the advancement of public policies focused on innovation and industrialization, strengthening integration between universities, the productive sector, and government.

Trends such as **network disaggregation (Open RAN)** and the growth of the **national software industry** are also expected to expand Brazil’s role in the next generation of telecommunications.

Origin and mission

Founded in **2023**, SMARTNESS 2030 emerged from the collaboration between **Unicamp, FAPESP, and Ericsson**, with the mission of advancing cutting-edge connectivity technologies and preparing Brazil for the 6G era.

Today, the Center organizes its activities into **five major research lines**—**NEWTON, DEMIST, C3LA, ADVENTURE, and DisCoNet**—which explore topics such as industrial automation, distributed artificial intelligence, edge computing, and cognitive networks, aiming to deliver concrete results that drive the evolution of telecommunications from 5G to 6G through 2030.

Leadership and contact

The Director of SMARTNESS 2030 is **Prof. Christian Esteve Rothenberg**, from the Department of Computer Engineering and Automation at FEEC/Unicamp. The Vice-Director is **María Valéria Marquezini**, a researcher at Ericsson Research and Development Center.

For more information, visit **smartness2030.tech** or contact the Center's Education and Knowledge Dissemination Manager, **Roberta Steganha**: **steganha@unicamp.br** | WhatsApp: **+55 (19) 99944-2012**.

Event details

SMARTNESS Studio 5G Inauguration

 December 3, 2025

 4:00 p.m.

 Congregation Hall – FEEC/Unicamp, Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil

About SMARTNESS 2030

SMARTNESS 2030 (SMART NEtworks and ServiceS for 2030) is an Engineering Research Center (CPE) supported by **FAPESP** and **Ericsson**, headquartered at Unicamp. With a total investment of **BRL 56 million**, the Center's mission is to conduct cutting-edge research, train highly qualified professionals, and drive technological innovation in **5G and 6G networks**, contributing to Brazil's scientific, economic, and industrial development.

About Ericsson

Ericsson's high-performance networks connect billions of people every day. With nearly **150 years of global operations** and **over 100 years in Brazil**, the company is a pioneer in communication technologies. Ericsson provides mobile connectivity solutions for service providers and enterprises. Brazil is the only country in the Southern Hemisphere that manufactures **Ericsson 5G radios and antennas**, at the company's factory in **São José dos Campos, São Paulo**, in continuous operation since 1955.

About NEC

With **57 years of operations in Brazil**, **NEC** delivers end-to-end secure information technology and network solutions for public and private organizations, telecommunications operators, and data centers. Its portfolio includes **Digital Identity** and **Safer Cities** solutions, supported by highly specialized teams, globally recognized proprietary systems, and a robust ecosystem of technology partners.